

Combining Knowledge Graphs and RAG for Enterprise Resource Planning

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Abstract. Generative AI applications for Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) need to bridge structured and unstructured content. Knowledge graphs (KGs) are known to represent both unstructured and structured data. They have been proven useful for improving results beyond baseline retrieval augmented generation (RAG). In this talk we show how we utilize Generative AI and Knowledge graphs for our use cases and also present our insights on Knowledge Graph Retrieval Augmented Generation (KG-RAG).

Keywords: Knowledge Graphs · Retrieval Augmented Generation · Enterprise Resource Planning.

1 Motivation

The SAP S/4HANA enterprise resource planning (ERP) software has an underlying data model comprising of hundreds of thousands of so-called ABAP³ base table definitions, connected via keys, foreign key and other relations. They are abstracted for application consumption via tens of thousands so called Core Data Services (CDS) views. Experts for over half a century have developed ERP solutions using such tables and views. An example ERP solution would reply on the implementation of a *Purchase Order* in an organization. The metadata associated with tables or views are present in various repositories, like the (i) S4 data dictionary, which provides ABAP table definitions or CDS view definitions (ii) A semantic keys repository that map tables to specific objects such as *Purchase Order* or *Purchase Contract*. (iii) An API definitions repository. A lot of the table metadata is also complemented by documentation that is present in various sources such as a developers, community, SAP Help and SAP internal learning hub data⁴. In addition to documenting e.g. the table structures and fields, these sources also provide valuable insights on the usage context of CDS views and base tables in various domain specific ERP solutions. In short, while the structured metadata may have succinct semantic descriptions of tables

³ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ABAP>

⁴ See an example: documentation of the [Virtual Data Model and CDS Views in SAP S/4HANA](#)

and views on their own, the diverse documentation gives insight into use cases and domain specific implementation know-hows. They are a treasure trove of community gathered wisdom that represents knowledge from the trenches.

Key Challenges Making the ERP knowledge searchable is a key challenge to be resolved for consultants, AI developers and various types of customers utilizing S/4HANA. As an example of this challenge, let us look at the persona of an AI developer looking to build ERP solutions for a *Purchase Order*. Without a search system, or knowledge of the S4 Virtual Data Model, the developers need to dive deep into documentation or talk to domain experts in time intensive discussions. Despite a lot of tables being related to one another and even used for similar solutions, there is neither (i) “Follow Your Nose” search system⁵ that helps a developer find connected tables or views for bottom up solutions, nor (ii) search system that helps in mapping business domain data to the right tables and CDS views. In the next few sections we show how KGs help in solving the above challenges, relying on both structured metadata and unstructured documentation.

Fig. 1. Combining conversational querying with KGs and RAG

2 Knowledge Graphs

2.1 KGs for retrieval on structured data

We generate the knowledge graphs on structured data for the common classes and properties in our target domain. Although the SAP S/4HANA has a huge amount of metadata, the underlying metadata schema needed for our use case is rather small and consists of less than 20 classes and their properties. Hence, we take the one time effort to manually create an ontology and scale across a wide range of frequent query patterns using these classes and properties.

⁵ <https://www.w3.org/wiki/FollowYourNose>

The knowledge graph is populated via ETL pipelines that process the metadata definitions from relevant repositories, data dictionaries and API definitions. This process makes the relations between tables in the graph explicit. In addition, for the common query patterns like "find base ABAP tables for a CDS view", query patterns are defined based on the ontology. [5] describes more details of this approach and how it compares to consulting an LLM for publicly available information about the S4 data model. We show that the knowledge graph on structured metadata and the fixed graph query patterns provide more accuracy and help to avoid hallucinations. [5] also provides a preliminary evaluation with a small set of questions provided by domain experts.

While modeling KGs this way solves the bottom up search problem of looking for tables and the "Follow Your Nose" problem, it suffers from the need to do manual modeling. In addition, the modeling based on the data model definitions does not encode all the documentation present in various sources. This means that this approach cannot provide answers to questions like in the left side of Figure 1. This is achieved by the SCC project described in the next section.

2.2 Retrieval on unstructured data

The SAP Consulting Capability (SCC) Project [4] [3] is a multi-stage conversational RAG [2] pipeline that is built on all documentation sources of SAP. Thus, instead of utilizing just an LLM on metadata, we now utilize our advanced Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) with a Document Grounding service [4] serving as the vector database backbone. This has enabled AI developers and consultants to ask and get answers to more descriptive queries like the one shown in Figure 1. SCC solves the problem of finding CDS views related to a domain that is not semantically captured in the structured metadata. In our talk we also plan to show insights on chunking strategies, document representation, embedding generation and prompt generalization.

2.3 Challenges in RAG

The diverse nature of the table metadata present across multiple sources introduced challenges like (i) Low precision when retrieving information from numeric attributes. (ii) Partial information retrieval due to information spread out across chunks (iii) Challenges in answering a global question across all sources (iv) Dominance of one source over another during retrieval. (v) Hallucination in similarly named tables and CDS views. In the next section we show how we utilized KGs on unstructured data to solve this problem

2.4 Knowledge graphs on unstructured data

To solve some of the RAG challenges and the drawbacks of hand curated ontology design, we focused on extracting information from unstructured text as

triples and translating them to a knowledge graph with nodes and relationships. The advantage of an unstructured knowledge graph is that it requires minimal amount of schema design. In addition, they can be generated at scale utilizing the latest techniques in KG generation. Using carefully curated prompts on SOTA LLMs, we generated unstructured knowledge graphs from multiple sources. These knowledge graphs went through a process of knowledge alignment to align and reconcile similar nodes. This resulted in a unified representation across various sources and various documents. We then created node2vec embeddings [1] with different embedding dimensions {128, 256, 512}. These embeddings were used in the RAG pipeline and have shown great initial promise. The same descriptive query about *Purchase Orders* retrieves information from diverse sources and also provides the links to nodes that can be then used to open the graph explorer as shown in Figure 1.

As of writing, the connection between the two knowledge graphs has only been explored with small examples. Hence, we see exciting potential in the research area of combining KGs encoding structured metadata and unstructured documentation in RAG based approaches and how they scale to include not just search results, but also actions in an agentic context.

3 Company Portrait

As a global leader in enterprise applications and business AI, SAP stands at the nexus of business and technology. For over fifty years, organizations have trusted SAP to bring out their best by uniting business-critical operations spanning finance, procurement, HR, supply chain, and customer experience.

4 Speaker Bio

Amar Viswanathan is a Principal Scientist in the Agentic AI group. He is the research lead for the SAP Consulting Capability. Felix Sasaki is the Chief Expert for Knowledge Graphs in SAP Business AI. He played a key role in the development of internationalization specifications at the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C), including the Internationalization Tag Set (ITS). Both the authors work on Knowledge Graphs, Semantic Web and NLP applications at SAP.

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